

THE SMARANDACHE PERIODICAL SEQUENCES

by

M.R. Popov, student Chandler College

1. Let N be a positive integer with not all digits the same, and N' its digital reverse.

Then, let $N_1 = \text{abs}(N - N')$, and N_1' its digital reverse. Again, let $N_2 = \text{abs}(N_1 - N_1')$, N_2' its digital reverse, and so on, where $\text{abs } x$ is the absolute value of x .

After a finite number of steps one finds an N_j which is equal to a previous N_i , therefore the sequence is periodical (because if N has, say, n digits, all other integers following it will have n digits or less, hence their number is limited, and one applies the Dirichlet's box principal).

For examples:

- a. If one starts with $N = 27$, then $N' = 72$;
 $\text{abs}(27 - 72) = 45$; its reverse is 54;
 $\text{abs}(45 - 54) = 09$, ...
thus one gets: 27, 45, 09, 81, 63, 27, 45, ... ;
the Length of the Period $LP = 5$ numbers (27, 45, 09, 81, 63),
and the Length of the Sequence 'till the first repetition
occurs $LS = 5$ numbers either.
- b. If one starts with 52, then one gets:
52, 27, 45, 09, 81, 63, 27, 45, ... ;
then $LP = 5$ numbers, while $LS = 6$.
- c. If one starts with 42, then one gets:
42, 18, 63, 27, 45, 09, 81, 63, 27, ... ;
then $LP = 5$ numbers, while $LS = 7$.

For the sequences of integers of two digits, it seems like:

$LP = 5$ numbers (27, 45, 09, 81, 63; or a circular permutation of them), and $5 \leq LS \leq 7$.

Question 1:

Find the Length of the Period (with its corresponding numbers), and the Length of the Sequence 'till the first repetition occurs for:

the integers of three digits, and the integers of four digits.

(It's easier to write a computer program in these cases to check the LP and LS .)

An example for three digits:
 321, 198, 693, 297, 495, 099, 891, 693, ... ;
 (similar to the previous period, just inserting 9 in the middle of each number).
 Generalization for sequences of numbers of n digits.

2. Let N be a positive integer, and N' its digital reverse.

For a given positive integer c , let $N_1 = \text{abs}(N' - c)$, and N_1' its digital reverse.
 Again, let $N_2 = \text{abs}(N_1' - c)$, N_2' its digital reverse, and so on.

After a finite number of steps one finds an N_j which is equal to a previous N_i ,
 therefore the sequence is periodical (same proof).

For example:

If $N = 52$, and $c = 1$, then one gets:
 52, 24, 41, 13, 30, 02, 19, 90, 08, 79, 68, 85, 57, 74, 46, 63, 35, 52, ... ;
 thus $LP = 18$, $LS = 18$.

Question 2:

Find the Lenth of the Period (with its corresponding numbers), and the Lenth of
 the Sequence 'till the first repetition occurs (with a given non-null c) for:
 the integers of two digits,
 and the integers of three digits.

(It's easier to write a computer program in these cases to check the LP and LS.)

Generalization for sequences of numbers of a n digits.

3. Let N be a positive integer with n digits $a_1 a_2 \dots a_n$, and c a given integer > 1 .

Multiply each digit a_i of N by c , and replace a_i with the last digit of the product
 $a_i \times c$, say it is b_i . Note $N_1 = b_1 b_2 \dots b_n$, do the same procedure for N_1 , and so on.

After a finite number of steps one finds an N_j which is equal to a previous N_i ,
 therefore the sequence is a periodical (same proof).

For example:

If $N = 68$ and $c = 7$:
 68, 26, 42, 84, 68, ... ;
 thus $LP = 4$, $LS = 4$.

Question 3:

Find the Lenth of the Period (with its corresponding numbers), and the Lenth of
 the Sequence 'till the first repetition occurs (with a given c) for:
 the integers of two digits,
 and the integers of three digits.

(It's easier to write a computer program in these cases to check the LP and LS.)

Generalization for sequence of numbers of n digits.

4.1. Smarandache generalized periodical sequence:

Let N be a positive integer with n digits $a_1a_2 \dots a_n$. If f is a function defined on the set of integers with n digits or less, and the values of f are also in the same set, then:

there exist two natural numbers $i < j$ such that

$$f(f(\dots f(s) \dots)) = f(f(f(\dots f(s) \dots))),$$

where f occurs i times in the left side, and j times in the right side of the previous equality.

Particularizing f , one obtains many periodical sequences.

Say:

If N has two digits a_1a_2 , then: add 'em (if the sum is greater than 10, add the resulted digits again), and subtract 'em (take the absolute value) -- they will be the first, and second digit respectively of N_1 . And same procedure for N_1 .

Example:

75, 32, 51, 64, 12, 31, 42, 62, 84, 34, 71, 86, 52, 73, 14, 53, 82, 16, 75, ..

4.2. More General:

Let S be a finite set, and $f: S \rightarrow S$ a function. Then:

for any element s belonging to S , there exist two natural numbers $i < j$ such that

$$f(f(\dots f(s) \dots)) = f(f(f(\dots f(s) \dots))),$$

where f occurs i times in the left side, and j times in the right side of the previous equality.

Reference:

F. Smarandache, "Sequences of Numbers", University of Craiova Symposium of Students, December 1975.